

CONTRIBUTION OF TOURISM IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF HAZARIBAG, JHARKHAND (INDIA)

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Tourism is a good course of action for transfer of real resources from capital surplus developed countries to developing countries particularly in context of liberalization of Indian economy and globalization of trade. The present study aims to indentify tourism development opportunities by identifying underdeveloped tourist spots for renovation in Hazaribag, Jharkhand, India. The study will also forecast the economic and social benefit for underdeveloped population from tourism development in Hazaribag.*

Design/Methodology - *To demonstrate the purpose of the present study, an extensive and systematic review of literature related to tourism development and their benefits to public from various secondary data base has been undertaken. More than 100 relevant research papers from reputed Journals like Emerald, Elsevier, Government information Quarterly, Springer were reviewed, of which 15 papers on tourism were picked for detailed review.*

Findings - *The detailed analysis of the reviewed relevant literature indicates the need of tourism development and renovation of tourist spots in Hazaribag in India. The analysis shows that it is essential to develop and renovate the tourist spots in Hazaribag that will help to uplift the social and economic standard of underdeveloped population residing in nearby areas from tourist spots in Hazaribag.*

Research Limitation/ implications - *The study is confined to published research papers and personal visit by the researcher to the proposed tourist spots in Hazaribag from chosen databases. There may be some published articles which could not be brought to our attention. Consequently, interpretation of the proposed tourism development opportunity in this study may be to some extent limited.*

Practical Implication - *This research paper contributes to tourism research by describing the impact of tourism development on social and economic upliftment of underdeveloped population. It is strongly expected that there is a significant relationship between the proposed tourism development & renovation of tourist spots and social and economic upliftment of underdeveloped population.*

Keywords: *Tourist Spot, Underdeveloped Population, Social, Economic.*

INTRODUCTION

For the last several decades tourism has attracted wide attention throughout the world. Each and every country of the world is paying rapt attention for its better development to gain foreign currencies and India is one of them. With a number of historical places, buildings, hill resorts, etc. India enjoys its prominent position all over the

globe. In fact, Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/ professional purposes. These people are called visitors (which may be either tourists or excursionists; residents or non-residents) and tourism has to do with their activities, some of which imply tourism expenditure (UNWTO). Growing of tourism industry without hamper of ecology in the 21st century is a major initiative. Hopefully, while protecting ecology, it would also generate high income especially in terms of foreign currency. Tourism is a good course of action for transfer of real resources from capital surplus developed countries to developing countries particularly in context of liberalization of Indian economy and globalization of trade. In geographical term tourism is a human activity and explores tourist resources as well as economic enchantment. The study can incorporate a variety of scales from tourist resources to landscape, resources to local landscape resorts etc.

Meaning and Concept of Tourism

In accordance with the The League of Nations (1936), a *foreign tourist* is defined as "someone travelling abroad for at least twenty-four hours". Hunziker and Krapf (1941) defined tourism as "the sum of the phenomena and relationships arising from the travel and stay of non-residents, insofar as they do not lead to permanent residence and are not connected with any earning activity. The Swiss professors Hunziker and Kraft further defined it technically in the year 1942 that 'tourism is the totality of the relationship and phenomenon arising out of travel and stay of strangers, provided stay does not imply the establishment of a permanent residence and is not connected with a remunerated activity'". The United Nations (1945) defined: "a person who travels abroad and stays at least for six months would be considered as tourist."

Evolution and Development of Tourism in India

India has a very rich cultural heritage since ancient time. The concept of '*Athiti Devo Bhaw*' (the Guest is god)' is primitive, and '*Vasudhauva Kutumbakam*' (the world is one family)' became bywords of Indian social behaviour. Since times immemorial, the rulers in different parts of India built luxuries palaces, an enchanting garden, marvellous temples, tombs and many more.

Presently the Ministry of tourism headed by the 'Union Minister for Tourism' is the nodal agency for the formation of national policies related to tourism. There is also a Minister of tourism to co-ordinate and regulate the policy in the state level. The administrative head of the ministry at the centre is the Secretary (tourism) and in the same way it is also there in the state level. In November 1982, the Indian tourism industry marked an important milestone because this year a policy was formulated and presented to the parliament called as National Tourism Policy, 1982.

Literature Review:

Some major facts are about tourism:

- To preserve Indian Culture and Heritage and project in the same to the world.
- To improve socio-economic condition in terms of employment, income generation, revenue generation, foreign exchange, etc.
- To offer opportunities to the youth of the country, not only for employment but also for taking up activities for nation building and character building like sports, adventure activities etc.

- To give direction and opportunities to the youth of the country to understand the aspiration and view point of others and helps in developing national integration.

The National Action Plan 1992

A National Action Plan 1992 was announced by the Government of India. It was an emerging action plan to set things right in some key areas, and to provide directions to achieve quick results. The objectives set out rightly stroked at the perceived inadequacies of the system and incorporate all those areas which have been identified as the weakness of India's tourism development policy.

The strategies outlined in the Action Plan for achieving these objectives were as follows:

- Improvement of tourism infrastructure
- Developing areas on a selective basis for integrated growth along with marketing of destination to ensure optimal use of existing infrastructure.
- Restructuring and strengthening of the institutions for development of human resources.
- Evolving a suitable policy for increasing foreign tourist arrivals and foreign exchange earnings.

The national action plan also mentioned areas of action which were important for tourism development which fall under the control of different ministries of the Government of India like improvement in facilities at international airports, liberalized chartered flights and open sky policy for routes on which Air India does not operates or operate in a limited fashion. These were important issues and most of them still need to be addressed.

The New Tourism Policy (2002)

In 2002, the action plan was finally translated into a tourism policy and it officially became a joint central-state government concern. The policy document attempted to establish tourism's great contribution in national development and its role as an engine of growth. It suggested that tourism not only generates government revenue, foreign currency, but also provides an optimal use of India's scarce resources, sustainable development, high quality employment (especially to youngsters, women and disabled people), and finally peace, understanding, national unity and stability. The policy aimed at increasing the number of domestic and international tourists. In order to do this, the government proposed to diversify the Indian tourism products and substantially improve the quality of tourism infrastructure, marketing, visa arrangements and air travel. In 2002, Government of India launched an international marketing campaign named as Incredible India to promote tourism in India to global audience. The Incredible India campaign projected India as an attractive tourist destination by showcasing different aspects of Indian culture and history like yoga, spirituality, etc. The campaign was conducted globally and received appreciation from tourism industry observers and travelers. However, the campaign was substantially criticized from some quarters. Some experts criticized it on its failure to cover several aspects of India which could have been attractive to the average tourist.

In 2009, the Ministry of Tourism launched a campaign titled "*Atithi Devo Bhava*" targeting the local population to educate them regarding good behaviour and etiquettes while dealing with foreign tourists. "*Atithi Devo Bhava*" aimed at creating awareness about the effects of tourism and sensitizing the local population about preservation of India's heritage, culture, cleanliness and hospitality. It also attempted to re-install a sense of responsibility towards

tourists and re-enforce the confidence of foreign tourists towards India as a preferred holiday destination. The concept was designed to complement the “Incredible India” campaign.

Research Objectives:

- To identify tourism development opportunities in Hazaribag.
- To identify underdeveloped tourist spots for renovation
- To forecast the economic and social benefits for underdeveloped population in nearby areas.
- To propose recommendations for the advancement of tourism in Hazaribag.

Hazaribag: A Prologue

Hazaribag literally means “a thousand gardens”. The city falls under the state of Jharkhand. It is a famous health resort situated at a height of 2019 feet above sea. It has excellent climate and scenic beauties all around. In the midst of the city dense forest is quite rich in flora and fauna. The Hazaribag plateau has on its eastern margin, Parasnath - the highest hill in Bihar (Jharkhand), rising to a height of 4480 feet. The loftiness here is of another order. According to the Jain tradition, no less than 23 out of 24 *Tirthankars* (including Parsvantha) are believed to have attained salvation in the *Sammetasikhara* of the Parasnath hills. The hill seems to have been an abode of Jains. The Prasvantha, 23rd *Tirthankar* was very popular among tribal population of Chotanagpur. He is identified by the snake king *Dharanendra*, whose many hoods protect the meditating *Tirthankar*. Both the *Swetamber* and *Digamber* Jains have many beautiful temples here on the hills.

Major Tourist Destinations of Jharkhand

The State has tremendous potential and tourist destinations to attract not only domestic tourists but also international tourists. There are three major destinations for tourists’ attraction. Firstly, Natural feature like Water Fall, National Park, Wild Life Sanctuaries, Lakes, and small hills make important tourists destinations. The second important tourist destinations are religious places like as Prasnath Temple, Chhinamstike Temple, Jagnathpur Temple, etc. and some special tourist places also attract tourists like Naterhat, Masanore, etc. Following are some major tourist places identified by Department of Tourism, Government of Jharkhand. These are given below:

Table 1: Tourist destinations

<i>S. No.</i>	<i>Themes</i>	<i>Tourist destinations</i>
1	Pilgrims	Deoghar, Paranath, rajrappa,janathpur, Temple Bharkali, Angrabari, Trikunti, Basukinath, Mahadev Sal, Maa Giri Rajeswari, kulbonga Mahadev
2	Waterfalls	Hundru falls Jonha Falss, Dassam Falss, Panch Grah Falls, Hirni Falls Lodh Falls,,
3	Wild life	Dalma Wild Life Sanctuary, Hazaribag Wild Life Sanctuary, Betal National park, Saranda-the Sal Forest, Plamau, Tiger Reserve
4.	Special Destination	Netarhat, Massanjore, Maithon

Tourist Traffic of Jharkhand

The table indicates the number of domestic and foreign tourists' visit to Jharkhand during 2007-2010. Figures available for past four years indicate that there has been a decline in the overall growth rate of tourism in the state. While foreign tourists have registered constant decline, number of domestic tourist has also dropped down probably due to lack of interest in promoting the state by inbound tour operators/travel agencies/tourist transport operators/ domestic tour operators and security reasons.

Table 2: Type of Tourist

Year	Type of tourist		Growth rate	
	Domestic	Foreign	Domestic	Foreign
2007	4906394	4004	-	-
2008	6030028	5803	22.9	44.9
2009	7610160	13872	26.2	43.1
2010	6885273	15695	-9.5	13.1

Source: India Tourism statistics, 2009 and 2010

Figure 1: Percentage share of top 10 States /UTs in Domestic Tourism

Source: Ministry of Tourism India

Figure 2: Percentage share of top 10 States /UTs in International Tourism

Source: Ministry of Tourism (India)

Major Tourist Destinations of Hazaribag (Jharkhand)

Jharkhand is one of the states in India which has tremendous potential for tourism. There is natural sightseeing as well as religious places. There are some very famous pilgrimage sites that attract people all over the globe. **Canary Hill, Wild Life Sanctuary, National Park, Hazaribag Lake, Suraj Kund, Chhinnamasta Temple, Silwar Hill, Suraj Kund, and Shrine of Hazrat Data Madarah Sah R.A. etc.**

Canary Hill

Canary Hill is about 3 KM from the Hazaribag town. There is a Dak bungalow on the top of the hill. There is another hill adjacent to this hill. One may see the whole view of Hazaribag from here. It is a beautiful picnic spot and may be visited in any season. There is a forest around the hill and wild animals may also be seen in the night by chance. Lake construction is also going on below the hill.

Silwar Hill

Silwar Hill is a beauty spot located at a distance of 5 miles from Hazaribag town on the road to Bagodar. A number of old images have been found at this place. In 1953 a temple was constructed where idols of Lord *Jagannath, Balbhadra* and *Subhadra* have been installed and a fair has been started on Ratha Yatra day. The place is now named '*Jagannath Dham*'. It is considered as an ideal picnic spot.

National Park

A national park has been constituted within the Hazaribag district for preservation of the fauna and to enable visitors to view wild animals in their state of freedom. It starts from about 10 miles from Hazaribag town on the Hazaribag-Barhi road and extends to east and west, but mostly westward for several miles. The total area is about 150 square miles with a core of right-free forest covering 80 square miles. Shooting is strictly prohibited in the

entire 150 square miles, but while the inner core of 80 square miles has been preserved in the state of nature and no cutting of trees or disturbance of the flora in any manner is permitted, in the outer fringe of 70 square miles normal exploration has been allowed. A number of watchtowers to view the forest and wild life have been constructed and a Forest Rest House built at Rajderwah, 18 miles, from Hazaribag. The National Park is a beauty spot. A number of dams have been built and more are in process of construction. The purpose is to create pools of water where the animals may drink in summer. Towers generally have been constructed above these pools so that in summer visitors may sit on these towers and easily see the animals that come to drink water. Artificial saltlicks have also been made for the animals. Roads have been constructed and are being extended. In addition to this National Park, the Koderma Reserved Forests have also been functioning as game sanctuary where shooting is prohibited.

Wild Life Sanctuary

Located on NH 33, Hazaribag Wildlife Sanctuary is counted among the most popular and significant sanctuaries in India. Deep thick forest cover and a *morum* road running through the wilderness provide an excellent opportunity to observe both flora and fauna. The Sanctuary is known for inhabiting deers, tigers, *nilgaaya*, sambhar and a variety of birds.

The main Sanctuary road ends at Rajderva before bifurcating to the Bahimar Gate of the Sanctuary. Rajderva has a small lake with Boating facility plus a forest rest house for tourists to stay.

The sanctuary is reported to cover an area of 184 sq. km. At Rajderva, a part of the sanctuary has been fenced and herbivorous animals, basically belonging from the deer family are securely kept in order to increase their population. One can very easily spot a variety of deer roaming fearlessly, playing with their mates or just chewing some herbs.

Hazaribag Lake

The most distinguished land mark of the town of Hazaribag is the Hazaribagh Lake. This area is most prominent which houses the bungalows of various civil servants, ranging from the commissioner to the judges of the districts. The lake is surrounded by AIR station and Urban Haat in the north, Ranchi Patna road in the east, the main town of Hazaribag in the south, and the Indira Gandhi Ballka Vidlaya in the west. The best view of the sunrise and sunset can be had from the lake. There is one Cafeteria in the middle of a large Garden to attract the tourist.

Chhinnamasta Temple

Chhinnamasta temple is located at Rajrappa, 28 km away from Ramgarh Cantonment along NH-23 in the Ramgarh district of the State of Jharkhand, India. It is situated on a hillock at the confluence of the Damodar and Bhera (Bhairavi) rivers near the Rajrappa Falls.

The temple enshrines the goddess Chhinnamasta (the beheaded Goddess Kali), one of the ten forms of the goddess Durga. The statue shows the goddess holding her own head in her left hand and her head drinking the blood oozing out of her neck. The headless idol of goddess Chhinnamastika stands on the body of Kamdeo and Rati in Lotus bed. Many smaller temples have been built around the main temple such as the temples of Ashtamatrika and

Dakshina Kali. The temples of Mahavidyas were built in a series. Some nearby temples located are Tara, Shodashi, Bhubneswari, Bhairavi, Bagla, Kamla, Matangi, Dhumavati.

Suraj Kund

It is located on GT Road, 60 km from Hazaribag, in Barkaththa block. Hazaribag road railway station is 31 km from this place. The normal temperature of water here is 169-190 degree Fahrenheit. Besides two hot springs, there is also a cold spring. The water has a therapeutic effect due to high Sulphur content. There are 5 *kunds* namely *Surya Kund*, *Lakshman kund*, *Brahm Kund*, *Ram kund* and *Sita Kund*. Besides these, a Durga temple is also located here. A big fair is held here every year on vernal equinox. A large number of tourists throng to this place in winter.

Shrine of Hazrat Data Madarah Sah R.A.

This is a holy shrine of saint Hazarat Data Madarah Sah R.A. Particularly it is regarded as the Muslims' pilgrimage. It is very close to Hazaribag Lake. Though he was a Muslim, the devotees who throng here every day cut across religion. This place can be developed into an important tourist destination site.

Economic and social benefits from Tourism development

Tourism attraction is regarded as a key concept of the tourism market and an important element in the tourism system, for they stimulate interests in travelling to a destination and provide people visiting these sites with satisfaction. They are magnet which attract tourist to a region, while at the same time stimulate for other tourism services (SwarBrooke J 2002). The district of Hazaribag is famous for the natural beauty as well as religious places but some tourist destinations need to be developed. According to the Samini et al. (2011), tourism has become one of the most significant export sectors in many developing countries. A general consensus has emerged that it not only increases foreign exchange income, but also creates employment opportunities, stimulates the growth of the tourism industry and by virtue of this, triggers overall economic growth. There are some tourist destinations like Canary Hill, Hazaribag Lake and Wild Life sanctuaries in the city Hazaribag. If Hazaribag is made as a tourist hub on a large scale, it may generate employment opportunities to the people to a great extent (India Tourism Statics 2009).

So far as tourism product is concerned it is different from other products. A tourism product is the combination of tourism services and offerings being provided by the different constituents of the tourism industry. The landscape, Lush Greenery, Wildlife adventure, stay in hotel, traveling, festival, tradition and culture of the host country/destination, etc. constitute the invisible and intangible structure of the tourism product. These must be identified and properly classified. (singh and pathak 2009).

Tourism is one of the world's largest growing and dynamic economic sectors in many countries and India is one of them. According to Ministry of Tourism Government of India, tourism sector generates \$100 in 2008 whereas it is highly expected that it will grow up to \$275 in 2018. The important rates of growth and development,

the volumes of inflow of foreign exchange, infrastructure development, new management techniques and the training experience are affecting different sectors of the economy, which are positively contributing to the economic and social development of a country (Surugiu Camelia 2009). Government of India, Ministry of Tourism has sanctioned 2371.19 lacks to Jharkhand while 1185.59 lacks has already been taken by the state government (Annual report 2011-2012, Ministry of Tourism, Government of India). The tourism industry generates multiple economic benefits to the receiving countries and to the tourism-sending countries. In the developing countries, one of the main reasons to sustain and promote tourism is the expected economic growth.

Tourism in India has emerged as an instrument of income and employment generation, poverty alleviation and sustainable human development. It contributes 6.23% to the national GDP and 8.78% of the total employment in India. Almost 20 million people are now working in the India's tourism industry. It is expected to reach to 1.56 billion by 2020, with the largest rate of increase in developing countries including India. It is expected to provide more than 251.6 million jobs by 2020. According to UN World Tourism Organization, 6-7% of the world's total jobs directly and millions more indirectly come through the multiplier effect of this sector. (Sharma et al.2012). Thus, so many job opportunities can be generated with the development of tourist spots, which can benefit the nearby areas as well as holistic development can be seen through the interaction of foreign and domestic tourists. The second most important thing is that Jharkhand is very rich in terms of tribe culture, tradition, and hand craft products. Tourism industries can also help promote peace and stability in developing countries like India by providing jobs, generating income, diversifying the economy, protecting the environment, and promoting cross-cultural awareness. However, key challenges like adoption of regulatory frame works, mechanism to reduce crime and corruption etc. must be addressed if peace-enhancing benefits from this industry are to be realized (Sapna Kakkar 2012).

Some areas need to be focused to improve tourism sector in Hazaribag like, rail network for good connectivity from Delhi, Kolkata and other metro cities especially to attract foreign tourists. One more important area needs to be improved in terms of three star and five star hotels (India Tourism Statistics, 2009) in Hazaribag. There is no facility of trained guides and Tourist amenities of international standard to entertain foreign tourists. Preservation of natural resources and heritage are important to attract foreigner tourists. Jharkhand is much known to Indian Media as well as international media for Maoist activities, therefore secure and safe tourism is the most important thing.

Conclusions & Recommendation:

The recent development in tourism made by the Indian government includes interest subsidies, exemption in income taxes and reduction in import duties. In order to boost up the tourism development in India, identification of thrust areas have been done. Significant improvements have been made in the increase of capacity of air seats, connectivity of trains to frequent tourist destinations. Accommodation facilities have been increased for better convenience of the tourists

Tourism industry in India is on the way of progress and development. It has vast potential for generating employment and earning foreign exchange. It is a good source to make country's overall economic and social development. Undoubtedly, the newly formed Jharkhand state has the potential to attract not only domestic but also foreign tourists. There is a need to take holistic approach and execute in terms of infrastructure, good communication, secure and safe tourism, and comfortable transport facilities. Hazaribag national park, wild life sanctuaries and Canary Hill can be developed as world fame tourist spots. These tourist spots need to be advertised at national and international level. The state needs to be positioned properly and in this endeavour the support of travel agents, tour operators, travel writers, representatives of travel and hospitality industry associations, experts in the tourists and cultural sectors, diplomats, journalists and other opinion leaders is crucial. The state government should make efforts for the development of these proposed sites. The existing sites should be given a facelift. Though the state government has taken steps for the betterment and upliftment of the tourist sites but a lot more need to be done. Efforts need to be in full swing to make Hazaribag, an important tourist destination. However, careful planning is required for effective management and exploitation of tourism potential in the city Hazaribag, Jharkhand so that it can also be helpful in socio-economic development of the region and the people living in Hazaribag.

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